

The Role of Communication Justice and Assertive Communication in B2C Marketplace Post Recovery Satisfaction

Kussusanti¹, Prijono Tjptoherijanto², Rizal Edy Halim³, Asnan Furinto⁴

¹Universitas Al Azhar Indonesia, Jl. Sisingamangaraja No. 2, Kebayoran Baru, Jakarta Selatan, Indonesia

²Universitas Indonesia, Kampus Depok, Jawa Barat, Indonesia

³Universitas Indonesia, Kampus Depok, Jawa Barat, Indonesia

⁴Binus University, Jl. K.H. Syahdan No. 9, Kemanggisan, Palmerah, Jakarta Barat, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The rapid growth of e-commerce, unfortunately, has not been supported by the improved services. Customers complaints have not been handled properly, due to the lack of non face-to-face communication. In the other hand, customers express their complaints in various ways, such as the assertive way. 317 respondents were collected as a sample of this research, who are B2C online customers in Indonesia, experienced service failure in the last 6 months, submitted a complaint and received a response. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used to analyze. This study proved that there was a positive influence of communication justice on post-recovery satisfaction. However, assertive communication did not influence the post-recovery satisfaction. This research also proved that post-recovery satisfaction has a positive effect on online repurchase intention. This research is expected to contribute to marketing science, and practical contributions are given.

KEYWORDS: communication justice, assertive communication, post recovery satisfaction, online repurchase intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

Around the world, e-commerce growth continues to increase. More online shops now provide variety offerings such as competitive prices, free shipping, and even lowest price warranty. However, service failures in online transactions appear differently compared to offline transactions (Gohary, Hamzulu and Alizadeh, 2016). In addressing this complaint, Forbes, Kelley, & Hoffman (2005) found that the type of service recovery will also be different from traditional retail. To explain the service recovery effort, some studies are using justice theory (Kuo and Wu, 2012). This justice theory is using three dimensions, which are procedural, distributive and interactional justice. Some researchers offer information justice as the four dimensions of justice theory (Gohary, Hamzulu and Alizadeh, 2016; Nikbin, Ismail and Marimuthu, 2013). However, there is a difference between information and communication. Information is a part of the communication process. Effective communication is required in a two-way services recovery, to ensure that service personnel can deliver appropriate information to what customer needs. Furthermore, effective communication in the service recovery process proved to positively affect post-satisfaction (van Vaerenbergh, Larivière and Vermeir, 2012). According to Shannon & Weaver (1964), effective communication requires the delivery of a message from a person's point of view precisely and in accordance with the point of view of others. Communication is placed in a deeper position in marketing activities, which involves listening, organizing and matching to customer needs (Duncan and Moriarty, 1998). Communication with customers will be more of a dialogue, and a question-and-answer process (Vargo and Lusch, 2004). From some of these statements, it can be seen that the meaning of information are being extended into communication, where the concept of information is more meaningful one direction, while communication is more two-way. Communication is the process of delivering information. Therefore, this research will see communication justice in service recovery process in online transaction and its effect on post recovery satisfaction.

Wirtz & Lovelock (2016) states that one way to deal with customer complaints and to address the occurrence of service failures is to keep customer informed about the progress of the situation. Customers do not like to be in an uncertain condition, since uncertainty or obscurity will results in customers being worried and depressed. Waiting makes customer uncomfortable and even angry, especially if there is no clarity of information (Taylor, 1994). Customers tend to be more accepting of circumstances if they know what is going on and receive periodic progress reports. In an online context, this is more necessary than offline transactions, since customers did not make the transaction by being present in the store and being face-to-face with the service personnel.

In online service recovery process, the delivery of information needs more attention, given that there are more limitations of communication media used if compared to offline. With the appearance of technology, information is not given in a face-to-face

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manner, but through electronic media; which support the fact that recovery of online services is indeed somewhat more difficult (Hart, Heskett and Sasser, 1990). Therefore, the right media for delivering information is needed in online transactions.

Customers have preferences for selecting communications media, such as by using technology indirectly or interacting directly with service personnel (Kattara & El-Said, 2014; Mattila & Wirtz, 2004; Shapiro & Nieman-Gonder, 2006). These communications media for the service recovery process can then be selected according to the needs, such as through special menu provided in the website, mobile application, online chat, e-mail, and phone. Relatively, face-to-face method is time, energy and money consuming. Making it not provided by most online stores.

When feeling the disappointment resulted from a service failure, customers can show different behaviours. Research on customer complaint behaviour proves that customers can be silent or complain in various forms (Day, 1984). Attitudes or ways of complaining customers also vary, with some being passive, assertive, or even aggressive.

Passive customers tend to avoid conflicts, unsure of complaints, or lack confidence in expressing their opinions and wishes. There is also an aggressive customer when venturing their feelings of disappointment (Bennett, 1997) by being rude, raising their voice or using harsh words and language (Richins, 1983), hoping to change things (Badghish, Stanton and Hu, 2015). While assertive customers will seek information, make requests, show disappointment, defend their rights, refuse offers, initiate, continue or break the conversation, and express anger and anger in a good way (Richins, 1983). Assertiveness reflects the feelings, attitudes, expectations, opinions and rights of a person directly, clearly and honestly, with respect to feelings, attitudes, expectations, opinions and rights of others (Galassi, M. D., & Galassi, 1977). Assertive customers do not resort to violence to defend or defend their rights (Fornell & Westbrook, 1979; Phau & Sari, 2004).

As far as the literature study has been conducted, no research has been found to see the effect of assertive communication on post-recovery satisfaction. In fact, the strategy most preferred for the company is to create conditions for customers to be assertive. By assertiveness, customers can convey clear information about the service failures and disappointments that they experience, and convey the desire or provide alternative solutions for solutions that can be taken. Thus, assertive behaviour is required in customer engagement during the service recovery process. This customer involvement positively affects customer co-creation in the service recovery process by sharing information and co-production, which ultimately affects perceive justice customers, and generates post-recovery satisfaction (Cheung and To, 2016). Customer engagement mediates the perception of fairness and satisfaction, in which customer participation in service recovery procedures is required for post-recovery satisfaction assessment (Gohary, Hamzulu and Alizadeh, 2016).

Another thing that will be seen in this research is about online repurchase intention. Post-recovery customer satisfaction has a positive impact on customer attitudes and behaviour, namely repurchase intention, word of mouth, customer loyalty, future co-creation tendency, trust, loyalty, and commitment (Gohary, Hamzulu and Alizadeh, 2016; Chang, Lai, & Hsu, 2012; Lii & Lee, 2012; Hoffman & Kelley, 2000). Bijmolt, Huizingh, & Krawczyk (2014) prove that the highest repurchase intention is in online customers who complains and are satisfied with in the complaints handling. Their research shows that customer with negative experience who complained and are then satisfied turns out to have higher repurchase intensity than customer who are not disappointed or disappointed but did not complain. This condition is called the service recovery paradox (McCollough, 2000; McCollough, Berry, & Yadav, 2000). On the contrary, some studies show that paradox service recovery does not apply in the context of online retailing (Lin, Wang and Chang, 2011).

However, being satisfied with the received service recovery did not close the possibility for customers to switch to another company (Forbes, Kelley and Hoffman, 2005; Weun, Beatty, & Jones, 2004). This is highly possible and likely even if they are satisfied with the recovery effort. In online transactions, this is easier because of one of their characteristics, which is easy to find alternatives to other companies, by simply opening applications or other online shopping sites on their smartphones. Therefore, customer loyalty becomes more difficult to achieve in the context of online than offline (Liang, Chen and Wang, 2008).

In contrast, Holloway & Beatty (2003) and Li (2015) stated that dissatisfaction with service recovery is not enough to make customers leave a company. Disappointed customers with the recovery effort, still tend to be loyal and shop at the same company in the future. With this inconclusiveness, it is necessary to conduct further research on the impact of post-recovery satisfaction on repurchase intention on online customers.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Communication justice

Justice theory derives from a social psychology theory, which is the main theory of consumer behaviour (Nee, 2016), and is widely used in various studies on service recovery. Perceived justice in the literature on service recovery refers to the perceived fairness of grievance handling, i.e. a sense of fairness about the treatment of a company when a customer complains. A person's judgment about fairness generally includes three dimensions, namely distributive, procedural and interactional. Distributive justice is justice regarding compensation for losses suffered by customers (Tax, Brown and Chandrashekar, 1998) due to service failure (Smith, Bolton and Wagner, 1999). Procedural justice is the justice in the process of delivering a result, involving policies and procedures used to solve problems or conflicts (Leventhal, 1976; Thibaut & Walker, 1978), such as service failure (Mattila, 2001). While

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interactional justice is justice about the treatment that a person receives as a decision, accompanied by explanation and sensitivity and respect. Thus, interactional justice emphasizes aspects of social interaction (Goodwin and Ross, 1992).

Furthermore, (Gohary, Hamzeli and Alizadeh, 2016) proves that there is a new dimension of justice theory that affects post-recovery satisfaction, which is informational justice. In the service recovery process, the company needs to provide timely, clear and timely information to the customer about the cause of the service failure and recovery actions to be performed. Verma, Sharma, & Sheth (2015) assert that because online transactions do not present human contact, and communication between sellers and buyers requires greater effort to improve the quality of relationships and build trust.

The importance of communication in marketing is affirmed by Vargo and Lusch (2004), which states that the purpose of marketing is not simply to communicate with the market, but to build a continuous communication process or two-way dialogue to the micro markets level even directed at each customer. This is in accordance with (Duncan and Moriarty, 1998), saying that marketing theory and communication theory have intersection. Both are in the midst of fundamental change, both in terms of impact and direction. There is a paradigm shift in these two areas, from models that emphasize more functionality, mechanisms, and product-oriented, that turns more into humanist and relationship-based models.

Many marketing roles, especially in the service industry, are essentially based on communication. Therefore, communication is placed in a deeper position in marketing activities, which involves listening, organizing and matching to customer needs (Duncan and Moriarty, 1998). In the past, most of the communications with the market were grouped into one-way communication and mass communication to convey the company's offerings to a particular market or market segment. Today, an understanding of service-centred exchange emphasizes that individual customers are becoming more privileged and transformed into deeper market relationships. Therefore, communication needs to be transformed more into dialogue-like, and a question-and-answer process (Vargo and Lusch, 2004). In the context of service recovery, the communication process becomes important because customers proactively share information which service personnel needs to listen actively and respond well.

Differently in e-commerce, the relationship between the company and the customer actually benefits with the existence of information and communication technology. Communication can be done faster, easier, and even cheaper than face-to-face communication, thus making it enrich the relationship values between the two parties (Hong and Wang, 2009). However, e-commerce communication requires more strenuous efforts because of the limitations of communication media being used, which is not in the form of face-to-face communication between service officers and customers. Kaur & Sharma (2015) states that companies need to provide a good communication channel so that customers can directly complain to the company.

Ching & Ellis (2006) states that in addition to offer many characteristic advantages, it turns out that online transactions through e-commerce can become a double-edged sword with the emergence of dehumanization of the relationship. Online transactions do not represent direct human contact, so e-commerce practitioners (click and mortar) have difficulty building relationships with consumers, rather than brick and mortar companies (Liang, Chen and Wang, 2008).

B. Assertive communication

After experiencing service failure, customers may use passive, aggressive or assertive methods to submit a complaint. Passive customers are silent customers (Fornell and Westbrook, 1979) or less able to complain (Bennett, 1997) with considerations such as time spent, shame, fear or displeasure with confrontation (Butelli, 2007).

Customers who complain after disappointment due to service failure are only 5% to 10%. The majority of the disappointed customers then stop being customers, switch to another company or spread negative word-of-mouth (Holloway and Beatty, 2003). Disappointed customers who do not submit their complaints to the company may pose a potential problem for some reason, such as making the company loses the opportunity to retain customers, the company's reputation may decrease with the negative word-of-mouth as well as the company losing valuable feedback about the customer's bad experience. As a result, the company cannot make repairs and prevent the same mistakes in the future. Like the iceberg phenomenon, there are bigger problems that are hidden and invisible. Based on this, the number of passive customers who do not complain is an "early warning signal" for the company.

On the other hand, aggressive customers are customers who use violence and force the will to change circumstances as they wish (Badghish, Stanton and Hu, 2015). They are less profitable for the business, since they can create potential harm. Aggressive customer aggravation proved to make the service personnel depressed and trigger negative emotions, even resulting in a burnout (physical and mental collapse) for being depressed. These symptoms can in turn negatively affect employee attitudes and behaviours and even decrease the effectiveness and productivity of the company (Yeh, 2015). For example, a service clerk cannot control their temper and turns aggressive towards the customer. Goussinsky (2011) and Svri & Olsen (2012) argue that aggressive comments from customers can lead to stress, emotional anger and reduce employee feelings of excitement.

Assertive is defined as a person's behaviour in an interpersonal context that reflects his feelings, attitudes, expectations, opinions, and rights directly, clearly, and honestly, with respect for feelings, attitudes, expectations, opinions, and other people's rights (Galassi & Galassi, 1977). Norton & Warnick (1976) states that an assertive person is able to communicate their intent verbally well and can argue well. An assertive person also actively speaks, leaves a positive impression on the other person, and guards their rights in dealing with others. (Rancer & Avtgis, 2006) states that assertiveness reflects the building characteristics. Someone who has

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assertive characteristic is able to achieve their personal goals while still creating positive feelings with others.

Polyorat, Jung, & Hwang (2012) defines assertiveness as an interpersonal behaviour undertaken to achieve certain goals in encountering obstacles or disagreements with others. Richins (1983) states that an assertive person shows their feelings and behaviours directly and honestly with respect to others. This behaviour is appropriate in several contexts of consumption, including seeking information, making requests, and showing disappointment. In other words, an assertive customer guards the rights of others and does not violate agreements with others. While aggressive customers use power such as threat or punishment to get what they want. Assertive customers show disappointment, defend their rights by informing, asking, and making requests.

C. Post-recovery satisfaction

Service recovery is the active action of the service provider company that is done immediately as a corrective action due to a service failure or something unexpected (Gronroos, 1988). While post recovery satisfaction refers to customer satisfaction of the corrective action of the company after the occurrence of service failure. This is different from customer satisfaction with service at the first meeting (Kuo & Wu, 2012; Mattila, 2001).

Wirtz & Mattila (2004) mentioned that customer assessment of service recovery efforts is influenced by two factors: service failure context (type and extent of service failure) and service recovery attributes (compensation, response speed, apology). With these factors, customers assess the performance of the company as long as service recovery is provided, through disconfirmation and perceived justice (distributive, procedural and interactional).

Several studies have shown that perceptions of fairness in service recovery processes affect post-recovery satisfaction (Tax, Brown and Chandrashekar, 1998; McCollough, 2000; Lin, Wang and Chang, 2011; Kuo and Wu, 2012). This service recovery process further impacts significantly on customer evaluation (Bitner, Booms and Tetreault, 1990). The company's service recovery efforts have an important impact on the level of customer satisfaction (Blodgett, Granbois, & Walters, 1993; Blodgett, Hill, & Tax, 1997; Berry, 1995). Customers value more important service recovery efforts than the actual early services. What resulted in greater disappointment was the company's failure to take action, not the service itself. In fact, service recovery can result in recovery paradox, a situation where customers who experience service failure and then receive service recovery, are more satisfied than customers who do not experience service failure (McCollough, Berry and Yadav, 2000). However, for online transactions, there is research that proves that service recovery can produce recovery paradox (Bijmolt, Huizingh and Krawczyk, 2014), others not (Lin, Wang and Chang, 2011; Maxham, 2001).

D. Online repurchase intention

Behavioural intention is an indication of a person's readiness to display behaviour that is the immediate cause of the behaviour (Ajzen, 1985). Behavioural intention may include repurchase intention and word-of-mouth, both positive and negative (Ortiz *et al.*, 2017). Repurchase intention is a customer's interest to buy back a company's products or services after receiving service recovery efforts (Smith and Bolton, 1998). Several studies have shown that service recovery is done to achieve customer satisfaction, loyalty and buying interest (Tax, Brown and Chandrashekar, 1998; (Smith, Bolton and Wagner, 1999) Smith & Bolton, 2002).

Various studies have proved that effective service recovery is important to the company, as it is not only a compensation for customer disappointment, but also can result in buyback, customer loyalty, trust and commitment, and positive word of mouth (Andreassen, 2000; Maxham & Netemeyer, 2003; Mattila, 2001; Tax, Brown and Chandrashekar, 1998). Post recovery satisfaction has been shown to have a positive effect on customer attitudes and behaviour, including repurchase intention and word of mouth (Gohary, Hamzeli and Alizadeh, 2016; Hoffman and Kelley, 2000). Similarly in e-commerce, transactions, post-recovery satisfaction has been shown to positively affect positive word-of-mouth, loyalty, and repurchase intention and co-creation tendencies in the future. On the other hand, poor service recovery will reduce a person's interest in buying. Service failure followed by failure of recovery, greatly affect customer switching. Customers will switch to other service providers, due to inconvenience, unethical personnel, lengthy waiting for no apparent reason, to harsh, coercive or dishonest behaviour of service personnel (Smith and Bolton, 1998). Easily online customers move from one company to another, making customer loyalty more difficult to achieve in the context of online than offline. Therefore required different strategies in running online relationship marketing.

III. HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

The conceptual framework of communications justice is derived from the concept of information justice, which concerns the explanation of why a service failure occurs. This requires the existence of justice in the explanation and justification of a decision. Information justice is not just about giving information about specific events, but also explanations about the rules or procedures made and the compensation given to customers (Ambrose, Hess and Ganesan, 2007). Customers tend to find reasons for service failures, which enable them to obtain information about good service procedures, and even allow them to share solutions for companies. Therefore, information justice takes precedence over the explanation of why a procedure needs to be followed and why compensation is given in a certain way (Colquitt, 2001). This perception of information equity increases if customers receive information that helps them make decisions (R. Folger and Konovsky, 1989).

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Furthermore, this information justice is positively associated with post-recovery satisfaction (Gohary, Hamzelu and Alizadeh, 2016). Informational justice needs to be considered as an important factor in online shopping, especially in the service recovery process. For example, the leader needs to sincerely share information with the customer and explain in detail why the failure of the service can occur. It can be said that informational justice is a key element in service recovery. In fact, informational justice is proving to make customers more loyal and satisfied, encouraging them to buy back and spread more positive word-of-mouth in both online and offline environments.

The process of delivering information is called communication. In order for communication to be effective, the delivery of messages must be in accordance with the point of view of others (Shannon and Weaver, 1964), involves the process of listening, organizing, and matching to customers needs (Duncan and Moriarty, 1998), as well as dialogue, and question-and-answering (Vargo and Lusch, 2004). Given the different meaning of information and communication, the hypothesis in this research is formulated to be: H1: Communication justice has a positive impact on post-recovery satisfaction.

(Fornell and Westbrook, 1979) and (Badghish, Stanton and Hu, 2015) proves that customers who complain to the company have a more assertive and more confident personality than a customer who complains to a friend (word of mouth) or does not complain at all. Customer who complain more assertively are able to defend their rights, file or reject requests, take the initiative to keep or break the conversation, and express anger well (Fornell and Westbrook, 1979).

Cheung and To (2016) states that in the process of service recovery, customer involvement is required so that it positively affects customer co-creation by sharing information and co-production, which ultimately results in post-recovery satisfaction. In this customer engagement process, the required attitude of the customer is assertive, not passive or aggressive. (Gohary, Hamzelu and Alizadeh, 2016) argues that customer engagement mediates between equity and satisfaction, in which customer participation in service recovery procedures is required for post-satisfaction assessment. Therefore, if customer assertively communicates their complaints, service personnel's responses are hoped to be positive which will results in an interactional justice. This will create what is called as co-creation process that will results in customer satisfaction.

Conversely, passive or aggressive attitudes have less ability in resulting co-creation, thus making it not being able to create customer satisfaction in service recovery processes. This is because customers' aggressiveness can make the service personnel depressed and trigger negative emotions (Yeh, 2015). Goussinsky (2011) and Sviri and Olsen (2012) also stated that aggressive comments from customers could cause stress and provoke emotions of service personnel. In detail, Gohary, Hamzelu and Alizadeh (2016) describes that customer involvement in online co-recovery will build a psychological relationship between the company and the customer, which in turn will reduce the likelihood of customers switching to another company in the future. Involvement in the service recovery process is needed to satisfy customers who experience service failure in online shopping. Customer engagement can create co-creation in the service recovery process. If customer involvement is high in the service recovery process, customers tend to keep their relationship with the company. This is affirmed by Guo, Lotz, Tang, & Gruen (2016), which shows that customers can value co-creation in determining service recovery through process control, decision control and information control.

The assumption that the customer is a passive recipient of a service recovery is no longer acceptable. Therefore, companies need to create conditions that encourage customers to be assertive. In fact, the importance of assertive communication is stated by Fornell and Westbrook (1979) who advise customers to participate in assertiveness training, both for passive customers (avoiding complaining) and aggressive (coercive). From this description, this hypothesis can be formulated: H2: Assertive communication has a positive impact on post-recovery satisfaction.

One customer assessment of a service is measured through behavioural intention, such as re-patronage intention, re-purchase intention, and positive word-of-mouth intentions (Jeon and Kim, 2016). Some research proves that the intention of repurchasing is the impact of customer satisfaction (Anderson and Mittal, 2000). A satisfied customer will have a significant positive tendency to re-purchase a product or use a service in the future. This also applies to customers who experience service failure and get service recovery. Smith and Bolton (1998) shows that customer satisfaction significantly affects the intention of repurchase after service recovery. Kuo and Wu (2012), Mattila (2001) and Smith, Bolton and Wagner (1999) also proves that post-recovery satisfaction affects the repurchasing intention. Xu, Yap, & Hyde (2016) and Roggeveen, Tsiros, & Grewal (2012) added that if the satisfaction rate in the recovery process coupled with co-creation increases, the tendency for repurchase intention will increase. Thus, it can be concluded that customers tend to repeat purchases after receiving service recovery (Maxham and Netemeyer, 2003).

Holloway, Wang and Parish (2005), Fang, Chiu, & Wang (2011), Kuo and Wu (2012), and Chang, Lai and Hsu (2012) proves that in the recovery of online services, satisfaction with recovery actions may have a strong effect on the repurchase intentions. Fang, Chiu and Wang (2011) said that the intention of repurchasing is most influenced by customer satisfaction than other factors. (Holloway, Wang and Parish, 2005) affirms that satisfaction is an important determinant of repurchase intentions. Based on this description, hypotheses can be formulated: H3: Post-recovery satisfaction has a positive impact on online repurchase intention. This theoretical framework is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

IV. METHODOLOGY

The population for this study is the customer in Indonesia who made a purchase transaction on the Business to Consumer (B2C) online store. This study uses non-probability sampling to determine the sample. Sampling method is done by purposive sampling method based on predetermined criterion of respondent (Cooper and Schindler, 2014). This is in accordance with the question and purpose of research. Prospective respondents who do not meet these criteria are not included in the respondents, and will be excluded from further analysis (Gohary, Hamzulu and Alizadeh, 2016). Criteria of respondents in this study are: (1) experienced at least one service failure when buying a product in one of the Business to Consumer (B2C) online stores in the last six months, (2) complaints and got handled (service recovery) from the online store.

In a study using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) analysis, the number of respondents ranged from 200 to 400. In addition, the number of respondents was at least four or five times the number of indicators or sub variables studied (Malhotra, 2010). The number of indicators in this study is 44, so the minimum number of respondents is $5 \times 44 = 220$ people.

With this survey method, respondents will be given number of questions related to behaviour, interests, attitudes, knowledge, motivation, opinions, and demographic data. The questionnaire is submitted online and the responses were collected in an answer form (Malhotra, 2010). Using Google Docs, online surveys are being sent directly through e-mail to the respondent by including link address that can be directly accessed. Respondents are welcome to answer questions in the link by clicking on the available answer options. The answers then went directly into the format of Microsoft Excel data that is ready to be processed.

This online survey technique is web-based and self-administered. This is reasonable given that the population of this study are online customers who have been accustomed in using and accessing the Internet. This data collection technique has been successfully used in several previous studies (Ghazali, 2011; Im & Hancer, 2014; Li, 2015). There were 869 incoming responses, but not all of them were in accordance with the respondents' criteria, so they could not continue to answer questions. While the one who meets the criteria of respondents, are welcome to answer the question to completion. 317 respondents were collected. Data analysis method used in this research is quantitative analysis, using model Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) with Lisrel program. SEM is a set of statistical techniques that allows testing of a relatively complex set of relationships simultaneously. The complex relationship can be defined as a set of relationships built between one or several dependent variables (endogenous) with one or more independent variables (exogenous), and those variables are constructed or constructed from several observable or measurable indicators directly (Wijanto, 2015). SEM can be described as an analysis that combines a factor analysis approach, structural model, and path analysis. SEM is a combination of separate statistical methods of factor analysis and simultaneous equation modelling model. The analysis to be performed includes analysis of measurement model, structural model test, and discussion of hypothesis test result.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Descriptive analysis

Of all 317 respondents, 54% are men and 46% are women. Most respondents are aged between 22-36 years (66%). Looking from the division of generations (cohorts), the results of this study shows that Generation Y or often called the millennial generation (born 1981-1995) are the most, followed by Generation X (born 1961-1980), then the Generation Z (born after 1995) and Generation Baby Boomer came last (born 1945-1960). This is consistent with research conducted by CPC Strategy (2017) that millennial are spending more on-line shopping (67%) than offline (33%), as opposed to Baby Boomers who shop more offline (59%) than online (41%) (Kelly, 2017). This is consistent with Valentine & Powers (2013) research proving that Y generation uses the Internet more often than other generations.

From this research, the most used communication media is online chat (46%), followed by e-mail (34%). This is consistent with the characteristics of the Y genes that prefer text messages as a way of communicating, rather than e-mail or telephone (ExecutiveVoice, 2016). Valentine and Powers (2013) also state that the Y generation uses less e-mail, but uses texting as their communication mode. This study also shows the least-used communication media respondents use to submit complaints are social media (3%) such as Twitter and Facebook. This is because the response tends to be less immediate than online chat.

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Correlation test between variables is done to see the discriminative validity. It is to see which construct is different from other construct, how big does it correlate with other construct (Hair *et al.*, 2009). In other words, this test is done to see whether there is a relationship between the research variables. Table 1 shows the square root of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each latent variable in this study, which proved to be greater than the quadratic correlation between each pair of latent variables. Thus, this test has proved the discriminant validity in this study.

Table 1. The mean, average variance extracted and inter-variable correlations

No.	Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4
1.	Communications Justice	3.18	0.90	0.860			
2.	Assertive Communication	3.86	0.69	0.435	0.787		
3.	Post-Recovery Satisfaction	3.06	0.97	0.823	0.388	0.927	
4.	Online Repurchase Intention	3.16	1.03	0.559	0.247	0.615	0.916

Note: Diagonal elements show the square root of average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct. Numbers below diagonal are correlations between constructs.

B. Measurement model analysis

The overall fit test of the model is used to see how well the data fit in for the model. The overall fit evaluation of the measurement model is checked on the value of RMSEA, NFI, NNFI, PNFI, CFI, IFI, RFI, SRMR, GFI, AGFI and PGFI incorporated as Goodness of Fit Statistics contained in Lisrel output. The results show that overall this study has a good match between data and models. Validity test is done by looking at the value of Standardized Factor Loading (SFL) of the indicator to its latent variable. The results show that all observed variables from COM1 to COM8, ASS1 to ASS7, SAT1 to SAT5, and REP1 to REP5, have Standardized Factor Loading (SFL) > 0.50, which means that all observed variables are valid for measuring their constructs (Hair *et al.*, 2006). Reliability test is done to see consistency of measurement model from latent variable of research, that is by calculating construct reliability value (CR) and variance extracted (VE) from standardized factor loading and error variances. The value of SFL of all variables of this study is above 0.50, which means very significant. While the construct has qualified its reliability requirement, that is the value of construct reliability ≥ 0.7 and variance extracted ≥ 0.5 .

C. Structural model analysis

In the structural model analysis, the overall fit of the model (Goodness of Fit), and causal relationship analysis were performed. To see the overall suitability of the model, some of the criteria used are RMSEA, NFI, NNFI, PNFI, CFI, IFI, RFI, SRMR, GFI, AGFI and PGFI. Overall, the results show good size. The causal relationship proved to be significant if the absolute value $t \geq 1.96$, and the research hypothesis is supported if the coefficient mark corresponds to the direction of the proposed relationship (positive or negative). The complete results of causal correlation testing can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of Structural Model

Hypothesis	T-value	Coefficient	Result
H1 Communication justice → Post-recovery satisfaction	15.76*	0.84	Supported
H2 Assertive communication → Post-recovery satisfaction	1.02	0.04	Not Supported
H3 Post-recovery satisfaction → Online repurchase intention	13.24*	0.66	Supported

*Significant with t-value > 1.96.

The result of significance test on hypothesis 1 shows that communication justice has a significant positive effect on post-recovery satisfaction (t-value = 15.76, coefficient value = 0.84). This means that hypothesis 1 (H1) is supported with data on this research. While the result of significance test on hypothesis 2 shows that there was no significant influence of customer assertiveness on post-recovery satisfaction (t-value = 1.02). However, the result of significance test on hypothesis 3 is proven (t-value = 13.24, coefficient value = 0.66), which means that there is a significant positive influence of post-recovery satisfaction on online repurchase intention. Therefore, hypothesis 3 is supported with data in this research model.

D. Discussion

Customer satisfaction after a recovered service failure can be measured from the customer's opinion, whether they are satisfied with the solution to the problem, likes the way of how the complaint was handled, whether the service recovery is provided as expected, whether the handling is good, and whether the handling is pleasantly done. These five indicators make up the post-recovery satisfaction. This study proves that communication justice has a significant positive effect on post-recovery satisfaction. These findings support the results of a research done by Gohary, Hamzulu and Alizadeh (2016) stating that information justice is positively related to post-recovery satisfaction and should be considered as an important factor in online shopping. From this research, it can be seen that the communication justice criterion is measured from the completeness and the clarity of information, delivered openly and immediately, and further information that is being provided. Communication justice is also considered good if the information provided is reasonable, appropriate to the needs, helpful, and delivered through communication media in accordance with customer choice, such as online chat, e-mail, or phone.

This supports the research of Colquitt (2001), stating that information justice takes precedence over the explanation of information about a decision, which includes clarity, transparency, accuracy, completeness and reasonability (Gilstrap and Collins, 2012). Customers expects clear and complete information on how service failure could happen, which will be perceived as useful and helpful for the customer. Moreover, an explanation on rules and procedure that is clearly communicated can also be helpful for the customer (Ambrose, Hess and Ganesan, 2007; Folger & Konovsky, 1989).

Furthermore, the effect of communication on customer satisfaction is in accordance with the statement of Ching and Ellis (2006), defining that communication openness is the process of sharing information between two parties in a timely manner. This is in accordance with van Vaerenbergh, Larivière, & Vermeir (2012) stating that communication in the service recovery process positively affects post-recovery satisfaction, provided that it is necessary to convey a message from one's point of view accurately and in accordance with another's point of view (Shannon and Weaver, 1964). Therefore, during communicating service personnel must be able to listen, organize and relate to customer's needs (Duncan and Moriarty, 1998), as well as establishing a dialogue, and question-and-answer (Vargo and Lusch, 2004).

The tested second hypothesis shows that there is no significant influence of assertive communication to post-recovery satisfaction (t -value = 1.02), meaning that hypothesis 2 is not supported. Assertive communication in this study is measured by an indicator of the ability to express disappointment, submits a complaint, and conveys information and desire, especially ones concerning on the solutions to solve problem. Viewed from justice theory (Gohary, Hamzulu and Alizadeh, 2016), post-recovery satisfaction can be achieved if online stores are able to provide distributive, procedural, interactional and informational justice. Therefore, post-recovery still will not be achieved if online stores cannot provide satisfactory compensation, simple procedure, friendly service, and effective communication; even if customers are already assertive when filing their complaints. This can be caused due to the lack of product knowledge from the officers. Vargo & Lusch (2004; 2008; 2016) states that information and knowledge (operant resources) is a major source of creating competitive advantage and achievement.

Another thing that made assertive communication does not affect post-recovery satisfaction is because communication via e-mail, online chat and website, contains only verbal elements. Mehrabian & Ferris (1967) stated that visual, vocal and verbal elements differ in their effect on communication effectiveness (55% for visual, 38% for vocals and 7% for verbal). Therefore, service officer faces a more difficult scenario to grasp the wishes of customers, given that they read complaints only on online chat or e-mail. Grönroos & Voima (2013) states that co-creation can only occur through direct interaction. However, interaction in seeking information is difficult to be created within the context of online services. This situation is exacerbated by poor empathy of service officers when interacting with customer. As a result, customer satisfaction can't be achieved even though the customer has complained assertively.

This research shows that communication justice has a very strong influence to customer satisfaction in service recovery (coefficient value = 0.84), but assertive communication from customer does not affect post-recovery satisfaction. This made companies unable to rely on the customer's way of (Kuo and Wu, 2012) conveying complaints and desires. This means that service personnel's ability to communicate can affects post-recover satisfaction more rather than customer's assertiveness.

In terms of online repurchase intention, this study proves that post-recovery satisfaction has a significant positive effect on online repurchase intention (t -value = 13.24, coefficient value = 0.66). This supports Anderson and Mittal (2000) research that states that the intention of repurchasing is the impact of customer satisfaction. The online repurchase intention in this study is measured by whether the customer will stay in transactions with the online store after receiving complaints handling, intending to buy more products in the online store in the future, or even for the long term.

The results of this study are also in line with Smith and Bolton (1998), Mattila (2001), Maxham and Netemeyer (2003), Kuo and Wu (2012), Roggeveen, Tsiros and Grewal (2012) and Xu, Yap and Hyde (2016), which proves that customer satisfaction with service failure and service recovery significantly affects repurchase intentions after a service recovery. In the context of online services, the results of this study support Holloway, Wang and Parish (2005), Fang, Chiu and Wang (2011), Kuo and Wu (2012), and Chang, Lai and Hsu (2012) which states that in the recovery of online services, satisfaction with recovery actions has a strong

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effect on repurchase intentions. In fact, Fang, Chiu and Wang (2011) states that the intention of repurchasing is mostly influenced by customer satisfaction than other factors.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The results of this study contributed in the justice theory study, which previously seen only from three dimensions, namely distributive, procedural and interactional justice. Communication justice proved to be the fourth dimension for justice theory, with eight indicators, namely completeness, reason, openness, clarity, speed of delivery, accuracy, benefits and information media used. Communication media used by customers in complaining is through phone, e-mail, online chat or menu on the website. On the other hand, this study shows the level of assertiveness of customers in complaints to online stores is quite high. However, assertive communication has no significant positive effect on post-recovery satisfaction. This is quite apprehensive, because assertive customers often do not get compensation, response, treatment and good information. In fact, a good service recovery cannot wait until customers behave aggressively (hard complaint). Companies need to facilitate so that customer is able to complaint in a friendly manner.

Due to the limitations of online communication as well as the attitudes of the less sensitive officers to the customers, many online customers have to express their complaints aggressively so that they receive the attention and recovery of the desired services. Therefore, it is highly recommended to the online store management to train the officers to have high sensitivity and empathy, and have active listening skills, especially because many customer complaints are delivered through online chat. Furthermore, this study proves that post-recovery satisfaction positively affects online repurchase intention. Therefore, an online store needs to believe that complaints and service recovery are opportunities for improvement.

To complement this research, further research can be done on customer aggressiveness as a way of complaining, especially in online transactions, and on how service personnel communicates in handling customer complaints, including several indicators such as active listening, empathy, employee assertiveness and emotional intelligence. To enrich and compare the results of this study, the scope of further research can be done on the C2C online store.

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